

Rac-3h

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-74-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	50	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 74 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/21/2022 3:00:36 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/21/2022 5:06:22 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.226	6946550	49.07	567927
2	10.488	7208479	50.93	394266

Asy-3h (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-75-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0122
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 75 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/22/2022 11:07:52 AM CST		
Date Processed:	1/22/2022 11:35:47 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.179	342664	2.94	20737
2	10.412	11318977	97.06	612113

Asy-3h (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	XT-3-75-2-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0121
Vial:	85	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 74 2
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/21/2022 3:38:51 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/21/2022 5:08:11 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.230	273683	2.27	21884
2	10.490	11780593	97.73	641077